

NEC's SMART Objectives Guidance

Goals are broad general statements that explain what the organization wants to accomplish. They summarize in simple language what the organization wants to achieve.

Goals must be: Simple, To the point, Free of Technical Terms and Easily Understood

EXAMPLE: Raise awareness about eating disorders.

Objectives must be Concise, Clear about their purpose, Self-Explanatory, Free of Technical Terms and Easily Understood. Objectives must be SMART, that is.....

Specific: WHO will be impacted by the program or activity? Examples: school-age children, librarians, museum visitors.

Measurable: HOW MUCH the participants will be impacted by the activity? Examples: Decrease misinformation by 5%, Increase attendance to health information classes by 10%, Identify 5 symptoms of eating disorders.

Attainable: HOW will the team realistically accomplish the objective? Examples: Teaching a class about mindfulness, organizing a book club about lived experiences of people with eating disorders; developing a workshop about useful community resources to deal with eating disorders;

Relevant: Does the objective align with or match the overarching goal? How does the objective relate to your organization's mission and values? Is it part of a coherent strategy?

Time-Bound: WHEN is the action taking place? Examples: Next month, during Y1 of the grant.

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	Question to Respond	Your Answer
Overarching Goal		
GOALS	In general, what do you want to accomplish with the activity/class/event?	
SMART Objectives		
S Specific	WHO will be impacted by the program or activity?	
M Measureable	HOW MUCH the participants will be impacted by the activity?	
A Attainable	HOW will the team accomplish the objective?	
R Relevant	Is the objective aligned with the overarching goal?	
T Time-Bound	WHEN is the action taking place?	
SMART OBJECTIVE	Write here your final SMART objective considering the 5 SMART characteristics	

SMART Objectives Template